

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Finnish farmers intention to apply cultivation with plant cover and shallow tillage

Farmers' perceptions of soil quality are of high importance in developing more sustainable farming practices. The farmer survey implemented in the SoildiverAgro project identified relevant agri-environmental problems in current production and the most effective farming practices to address these issues. The survey data was collected from six different regions in Europe. In Finland, 357 farmers responded to the survey, with 71% being conventional farmers and 29% organic.

In Finland, the survey measured farmers' interest in applying combined plant cover and shallow tillage. Of the respondents, 61% were certainly interested in applying it in the future, 25% were hesitant, and 14% were negative. There were no significant differences in interest between organic and non-organic farmers.

In Finland, soil moisture and structure were emphasized in evaluating the impacts of plant cover and shallow tillage. However, weed pressure was also perceived as an important impact of the practice. Environmentally oriented peer farmers' opinions were seen as encouraging the use of the practice. As a controlling factor, farmers perceived policy instruments, especially the possibility of subsidies, as influential. The intention to use the practice in the future was particularly determined by previous experiences and attitudes towards the practice. Additionally, the belief that the practice can reduce runoff positively affected farmers' interest in applying it.

1. Finnish farmers had high interest in applying combined plant cover and shallow tillage.

KEYWORDS

New practices, intention to apply, cultivation with plant cover, shallow tillage

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